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Research Article

**AN ASSESSMENT ON NURSING IS THE CARE OF PATIENTS:
THE PERCEPTION OF NURSES TOWARDS MALE PATIENTS****¹Dr. Attiya Arif, ²Dr. Jabbar Ahmad, ³Dr. Muhammad Shayan Waseem****¹Central Park Teaching Hospital Lahore, ²Casualty Medical Officer, Fatima Memorial Teaching Hospital, Lahore, ³Medical Officer, BHU Chishti Qutab Din.****Abstract:**

Objective: The most important function of the nursing is the care of patients. It is the duty of nurses to care about the male patients with no bias. The perceptions of sexuality & humiliation impact negatively on close care mainly among men patients & female nursing staff. In this research work, the main aim was to find out the behavior of nurses towards male patients & assess the factors that determine nurses' attitudes, towards male patients and evaluate some factors that can work for the betterment of the condition.

Methodology: This transverse research work conducted from March to June of the year 2019. Three hundred student nurses participated willingly out of three hundred and ten students and gave response to the questionnaires. There were total twenty-nine questions in the questionnaire in which eight questions were about the socio-demographic traits of the nurse and twenty-one questions were about their behavior to the male patient.

Results: Results displayed that 71.3% students showed that the performance of any action to male patient was very easy as the performance on the female patient of 78.3% displayed that the male patient of the same age were very complicated group of age for take care. The measured behavior point of the students of third about cleaning of body, rectal lavage, application of rectal and the application of the nasal-gastric tube are very high than the students of other years. In the same manner, the behavior was more optimistic among students that who chose their nursing school deliberately than the other students.

Conclusion: Majority of the students have pessimistic behaviors towards the particular physical care requirements of the male patients, particularly the application on the genital area. Application of the awareness procedures, professionalism & provision of the information of the ethics and insight can solve this issue.

Key Words: Nurse, attitude, behavior, pessimistic, optimistic, physical, genital, provision, ethics, methodology.

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INTRODUCTION:

The most important duty of the nursing is the care of the patient [1, 2]. The responsibility of the nurses is to care the male patients with no bias. Nursing is a profession in which females are dominated in the whole world [3, 4] this may aggravate the negative impacts which are due to the pessimistic behavior of nurses at the time of providing genital care to males. Nurses make use of desexualization & diversion to handle these types of conditions [5]. The values of the culture effect these views but the research works display that these types of perceptions exists in less or high quantity in all the countries of the whole world [6]. Xiang interrogated the female nurses of China to know about their psychological responses at the time of providing care to the private areas of males. Ninety percent students reported that they have many mental issues as aversion & mental stress, uneasiness, blushing & more than ninety-five percent believed that it was better for the male gender to perform these types of works [7]. It is the duty of the nurses to perform their duties with no discriminations and with no preference to any gender. The law of many countries has banned the discrimination of the gender in the healthcare services [8, 9]. In USA, sex can be a professional qualification standard just for the care takers of mental health [10]. In this research work, the main aim was to find out the attitude of the female nurses to the male patients & assess some features which can work in the betterment of this condition.

METHODOLOGY:

This transverse research work conducted from March to June 2019 in a nursing school. At the time of this

research work, there were three hundred and ten students in the school. Three hundred female nurses willingly entered in the research work and gave response to the questionnaires. Questionnaire was used as a tool of data collecting. In that questionnaire, 8 questions were about the socio-demographic traits of the nurses and twenty-one questions were about their behavior towards the care of male patients. The questionnaires filling carried out under complete observation. SPSS software version fifteen was in use for the evaluations of the results. Frequencies & percentages were in use for the representation of the variables. The comparison of the groups carried out with the help of chi square tests [11].

RESULTS:

Three hundred nurse students participated in the research work. Majority of the students was from 2nd year of study constituting more than twenty-eight percent of the total amounts. About 38.7% students concluded that the level of their father education as graduate of high school & this rate found as 28.3% for the level of mother education. Sixty-two percent students were living in the city areas. Majority of the students (71.3%) stated that the performance of the applications on male patient was very easy as handling the female patient, 78.3% students displayed that the most difficult age group was of same age for taking care. Only 5.3% students concluded that they had a past of negative knowledge as described in Table-1.

Table-I: Opinions of participants about some patient care issues (Ankara, 2009).

Parameters		n	%
Have you chosen your school intentionally?	Yes	216.0	72.00
	No	84.0	28.00
Do you make gender discrimination between your patients?	Yes	13.0	4.30
	No	287.0	95.70
Is performing any application to a male patient as easy as performing to a female patient?	Yes	221.0	71.30
	No	86.0	28.70
Which is the most difficult age group for taking care?	Kids	27.0	9.00
	My peers	235.0	78.30
	Aged	38.0	12.70
Have you ever had a negative experience while taking care of male patient?	Yes	16.0	5.30
	No	284.0	94.70

Students of 3rd Year approved that the age of the patients has an impact on the behavior of the nurses as elaborate in Table-2.

	Grades				p*
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	
Gender of patient	3.60	4.70	3.00	7.70	0.1010
Education level of patient	77.10	85.80	77.60	73.80	0.0610
Age of patient	40.90	48.20	74.60	30.80	<0.001
Patient care environment	48.20	42.40	67.10	38.50	0.0860
Compliance of patient	84.00	94.10	89.60	84.60	0.3670
Expressions of patients	33.70	37.70	47.80	36.90	0.5120

* Chi square test

Most pessimistic view was available in the students of 3rd year. These disparities were significant statistically as mentioned in Table-3.

Table-III: Attitudes of students by their grades about delivery of care (Ankara, 2009).

Applications	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	p*
Urinary catheter applications	22.90	17.60	31.30	23.10	0.2870
Body cleansing	20.50	11.80	29.80	16.90	0.0120
Rectal lavage	27.70	12.90	35.80	24.70	0.0060
Perennial cleansing	25.30	15.30	49.20	27.20	<0.001
Mouth care	7.20	2.40	3.00	1.50	0.1800
Rectal tube application	16.90	10.60	32.90	26.10	0.0040
Hair cleansing	4.80	1.20	1.50	0.00	0.5850
Intramuscular injection on back	6.00	1.20	1.50	1.50	0.4900

* Chi square test

The residence regions of family of students having any professional in the health service did not impact the sex discrimination or the students who deliberately chose this profession showed that these students have the most optimistic views as mentioned in Table-4.

Table-IV: Evaluation of some possible variables that effected gender discrimination and provision of care				
Is gender of your patients a problem for you?				
		Yes n (%)	No n (%)	p*
Family settlement	Village	1.0 (4.20)	23.0 (95.80)	0.483
	Country	2.0 (2.20)	88.0 (97.80)	
	Urban area	10.0 (5.40)	176.0 (94.60)	
Health professional in family	Yes	48.0 (72.70)	18.0 (27.30)	0.777
	No	166.0 (70.90)	68.0 (29.10)	
Have you chosen your school intentionally?	Yes	158.0 (73.10)	58.0 (26.90)	0.265
	No	56.0 (66.70)	28.0 (33.30)	
Have you ever had a negative experience while taking care of male patient?	Yes	14.0 (87.50)	2.0 (12.50)	0.167**
	No	200.0 (70.40)	84.0 (29.60)	
Is performing any application to a male patient as easy as performing to a female patient?				
Family settlement	Village	15.0 (62.50)	9.0 (37.50)	0.232
	Country	60.0 (66.70)	30.0 (33.30)	
	Urban area	139.0 (74.70)	47.0 (25.30)	
Health professional in family	Yes	1.0 (1.50)	65.0 (98.50)	0.203**
	No	12.0 (5.10)	222.0 (94.90)	
Have you chosen your school intentionally?	Yes	5.0 (2.30)	211.0 (97.70)	0.006
	No	8.0 (9.50)	76.0 (90.50)	
Have you ever had a negative experience while taking care of male patient?	Yes	1.0 (6.30)	15.0 (93.70)	0.517**
	No	12.0 (4.20)	272.0 (95.80)	

* Chi square test **Fischer's exact test

DISCUSSION:

There were some research works present in Turkey about the role of gender and nursing but this research was particular with a unique topic. The study of the new features about the perceptions of the nurses carried out. In this research work, new results addition carried out from the point of view of nurses. Tortumluoglu stated that gender role is very important in the field of nursing and this condition has a trans-cultural status. She gave pinion that in various countries the sex of the caregiver impacts upon the quality of the health care quality [6]. Another feature of that problem is the opinion of the patient. Ozbasaran concluded that about sixty-three percent patient showed that gender of doctors was not of much importance but about seventy-two percent among

them gave preference to the female nurse. Almost all the female patients preferred the female nurses.

An association between the gender of the patient and the gender of the female was available [12]. Steinke & Patterson concluded that fifteen percent nurses gave the data about the issues of sex of their patients [13]. In Turkey, Yildiz & Pinar concluded that about ninety-seven percent patients did not provide the data about sex even there was a requirement to tackle the issues [14]. But some scholars have declared that the shortage of time was another problem. This output give favor that both patients & nurses like the gender of each other. In this research work, about ninety-five percent student nurses showed that the application of any method to the female patient was very easy as compared to the male patient. About seventy-three

percent nurses have the view that they have created the discrimination of the gender in a few care practices.

This research states that similar to the nurse students of the various countries [15-17], female nurses of Turkey may think some activities of care as embarrassing. Zang concluded that female nurses of China displayed that they always felt stress about the care of genital areas, shaving of the pubic area & removal of the urinary catheter removal [18, 19]. In this research work, nurse students stated that they have problems about the perennial cleansing (twenty-eight percent), rectal lavage (twenty-four percent) & application of urinary catheter (twenty-three). These findings show that that is a trans-cultural problem. Chur Hansen & Pomfret found that the technical complications may affect the perception of the nurses [17, 20]. In many research works, it was concluded that nurses may look upon perineal cleaning, catheterization of the urinary duct etc. as filthy [15, 21-23].

About 78% nurse students stated that the most difficult age group of male for providing care was peers. Attendants displayed that the care of the children & patients old age was much easy as compared to the peers. Hweidi concluded the same outcome in the nurses of Jordan [24]. Because it was the 1st study of such nature so it has some hindrances. There was not any scale available to measure the attitude of the nurses. The research work performed among the students in the nursing field. The behavior can alter after the completion of degree or attaining professionalism.

CONCLUSIONS:

The attitude of majority of the nurse students was pessimistic towards the male patients particularly applications of the methods on genital area. The conventional local culture cannot explain such outcomes. The gain of the professionalism can decrease the negative attitude of the students. The awareness program and provision of the ethical data can improve this condition. Applied education methods and providing ethical information can help improve this situation.

REFERENCES:

1. Karagozoglu S. Nursing as a scientific discipline. Cumhuriyet University J School of Nursing 2005; 9:6-19. (Turkish)
2. Ellis J, Hartley C. Nursing in today's world: Trends, issues & management: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. 2004.
3. Anthony A. Retaining Men in Nursing--Our Role as Nurse Educators. Annual Review of Nursing Education: Innovations in Curriculum, Teaching, and Student and Faculty Development, 2005: 211.

4. Evans J. Men nurses: A historical and feminist perspective. J Adv. Nurs.2004;47:321-328. Yusuf Ziya Turk et al.
5. Edwards S. An anthropological interpretation of nurses' and patients' perceptions of the use of space and touch. J Adv Nurs. 1998;28(4):809-817.
6. Tortumluoglu G. Transcultural nursing and cultural care models, Cumhuriyet University J School of Nursing. 2004; 8:47-57. (Turkish).
7. Xiang H, Dong XLL. Investigation on female nurses' mental state of male patients while manipulating their privacy. J Nurs Sci. 2004; 19:6-8.
8. Hendrick J. Law and ethics in nursing and health care: Nelson Thornes. 2000.
9. Rumbold G. Ethics in nursing practice: Bailliere-Tindale. 1999.
10. Staunton P, Chiarella M. Nursing & the law: Churchill Livingstone, Sydney; Edinburgh. 2004.
11. Acikel CH, Kilic S. Selecting Statistical Methods in Medical Researches. TAF Preventive Medicine Bulletin. 2004;3(7):162-163.
12. Ozbasaran F, Taspinar A, Cakmakci A. What are patients think about the Gel/der of the people W/w look after them? Ataturk University, J Nursing School 2002;5:62-68. (Turkish)
13. Steinke E, Patterson P. Sexual counseling of MI patients by cardiac nurses. J Cardiovascular Nursing. 1995;10(1):81-87.
14. Yildiz H, Pinar R. Sexual dysfunction in patients with myocardial infarction. Anadolu kardiyoloji dergisi: Anatolian J Cardiology. 2004; 4:309-317.
15. Seed A. Crossing the boundaries--experiences of neophyte nurses. J Adv Nurs. 1995; 21:1136-1143.
16. Wolf ZR, Bender PJ, Beitz JM, Wieland DM, Vito KO. Strengths and weaknesses of faculty teaching performance reported by undergraduate and graduate nursing students: A descriptive study. J Professional Nursing. 2004; 20:118- 128.
17. Pomfret I. Urinary catheters: selection, management and prevention of infection. British J Community Nursing. 2000;5(1):6-13
18. Zang Y, Chung L, Wong T. A review of the psychosocial issues for nurses in male genitalia-related care. J Clin Nurs. 2008; 17:983-998.
19. Zang Y, Chung L, Wong T, Chan M. Chinese female nurses' perceptions of male genitalia-related Care-Part 2. J Clin Nurs. 2009; 18:826-837.
20. Chur-Hansen A. Preferences for female and male nurses: The role of age, gender and previous experience. J Adv Nurs. 2002; 37:192-198.

20. Williams A. A literature review on the concept of intimacy in nursing. *J Adv Nurs*. 2001; 33:660-667.
21. Twigg J. Carework as a form of bodywork. *Ageing and Society*. 2000; 20:389-411.
22. Jervis L. Working in and around the chain of command': Power relations among nursing staff in an urban nursing home. *Nursing Inquiry*. 2002; 9:12-23.
23. Hweidi I, Al-Obeisat S. Jordanian nursing students' attitudes toward the elderly. *Nurse Education Today*. 2006; 26:23-30.